

**XIX ASR OXIRI XX ASR BOSHLARIDA TURKISTONDA MAHALLIY
MATBUOTNING VUJUDGA KELISHI VA RIVOJI**

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Annotatsiya. XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmida Rossiya imperiyasi tomonidan bosib olingan O'rta Osiyo hududlarida yashovchi xalqlarning siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy hayotida keskin o'zgarishlar yuz berdi. Shu bilan birga XX asr boshlarida o'lkamizda matbuot dastlab rus ma'muriyati so'ngra jadid namoyondalari tomonidan rivoj topishi borasida harakatlar boshlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: Matbuot, Turkiston gazetasi, mafkura, "Ruskiy Turkistan", "Taraqqiy" Toshkent, Jadid, "Samarqand", mahalliy, Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy, Munavvarqori Abdurashidxonov, Abdulla Avloniy, Abdurauf Fitrat.

XIX asr oxiri XX asr boshlarida Turkistonda yuz bergan siyosiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy o'zgarishlar natijasida milliy matbuot shakllana boshladi. Bu davr Rossiya imperiyasi mustamlakachiligi kuchaygan, ammo shu bilan birga jadidchilik harakati orqali xalq orasida uyg'onish boshlangan davr edi. Aynan shu jarayonlar natijasida o'lka matbuoti ham rivojlanish yo'liga tushdi. Turkistonda ilk matbuotning shakllanish tarixi 1870-yil aprelda chiqq boshlagan "Turkiston viloyatining gazetasi" bilan boshlangan. "Turkiston general-gubernatorligi buyrug'i bo'yicha ushbu oydan boshlanib "Turkiston gazetasi" chiqadur. Ushbu gazetalarda barcha xaloyiqg'a ma'lum bo'lmoq uchun general-gubernatorni har turli farmoni izhor qilinur va yana har turli yangi xabarlar, savdo to'g'risida yozilur va yana Toshkand va g'ayri shaharlarda bo'lg'on hodisa-voqealar yozilur", deyilgan edi gazetaning dastlabki sonlaridan birida. Turkistonda ruslashtirish siyosatini amalga oshirishda rus hukumati turli usul va vositalardan foydalandi. Bu usullardan biri targ'ibot-tashviqot bo'lib, hatto yerli xalq vakillari faoliyatidan ham ustamonlik bilan foydalandi. Ana shu maqsadda "Turkiston viloyatining gazetasi" general-gubernatorlik qoshida chop etilayotgan "Turkestanskiye vedomosti" gazetasiga ilova sifatida chiqarila boshlangan edi. O'lka hayotini butun muammolari bilan yoritadigan, milliy masalalarni keng qamrab olgan va dunyodagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy o'zgarishlar haqida xolis axborot bera oladigan

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matbuot kerak edi. Bunday matbuotni yaratishni esa taqdir taqozosi bilan jadidlar o'z zimmasiga oldilar. XX asr boshida jiddiy tus olgan jadidchilik faoliyatining eng muhim tarmog'i bo'lmish milliy matbuotning shakllanishi muhim ahamiyatga ega voqea sifatida maydonga keldi. Turkiston matbuoti tarixida bu gazetalar kabi uzoq muddat davomida uzluksiz chiqqan boshqa davriy nashr bo'lgan emas. Bu gazetalar mustamlakachi ruslarning Turkiston ma'muriyati mablag'i hisobidan nashr qilinib, shu ma'muriyatning rus va o'zbek tilidagi rasmiy matbuot nashri vazifasini o'tagan va o'lkada mustamlakachilik siyosatini o'tkazish vositasi bo'lib xizmat qilgan. Birinchi rus inqilobi (1905-1907) dan so'ng rus hukumati sarosimaga tushib qoldi va matbuot sohasida biroz yon berishga majbur bo'ldi. Ilg'or musulmon ziyolilari bu vaziyatdan foydalanib, davriy nashrlar chiqarish to'g'risida ruxsatnoma olishga erishadilar. Shunday qilib, avval Toshkentda, keyinroq Samarqand, Qo'qon va Buxoroda birin-ketin ijtimoiy-siyosiy va adabiy mazmundagi bir qator o'zbek tilidagi davriy nashrlar paydo bo'ldi. Ularning tashkilotchilari, muharrir va mualliflari XIX asr oxiri XX asr boshlarida Turkistonda ma'rifatchilik zamirida yuzaga kelgan jadidchilik harakatining mafkurachilari bo'lishdi. Jadidlar rus istilochilari va mahalliy mustabidlar tazyiqi ostida qolgan Turkiston o'lkasini savodli, ma'rifatli, taraqqiyotga erishgan, obod yurtga aylantirish orzusi bilan yashadilar va matbuotni shu orzuga erishish yo'lidagi qudratli vosita deb bildilar. Turkiston jadidlarining yetakchi namoyondalari Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy, Munavvarqori Abdurashidxonov, Abdulla Avloniy, Abdurauf Fitratlar taraqqiyparvar yo'nalishdagi o'zbek matbuotini shakllantirishga juda katta hissa qo'shdilar. 1905-yildagi inqilobiy to'lqinlarning tasirida "Ruskiy Turkistan" va "Samarqand" gazetalarning rahbarligi bolsheviklar qo'lga o'tib ketdi. Podsho hukumati bu gazetalar faoliyatini taqiqlab qo'ygach ular o'z nomlarini o'zgartirib: "Turkiston", "Vperyod", "Ruskiy Turkistan", "Zarafshan", "Novoy Samarqand", "Ruskiy Samarqand" nomlari ostida chiqarila boshlaydi. 1906-yilga kelib bu gazetalarni chop etish umuman taqiqlab qo'yiladi. XX asrning boshlariga kelib mahalliy milliy matbuotni yo'lga qo'yish borasidagi say-harakatlar ijobiy yakunlanadi. 1906-yilda Toshkentda birinchi marta o'zbek tilida "Taraqqiy" gzetasi chiqariladi. Bu o'zbek milliy matbuotining ilk debochasi sifatida tarixga kiradi. Shundan so'ng birin - ketin, yangi-yangi matbuot organlari vujudga kela boshlaydi. Toshkentda "Sadoi Turkiston" gazetasi jadidlar tomonidan chiqarila boshlaydi. Ma'lum muddat Turkistonda matbuot to'xtab qoldi, bunga sabab, hukumatning matbuot bo'yicha senzurasining kuchayishi bo'ldi. 1913-yildan boshlab yana matbuot nashrlarining yo'lga qo'yilganligini kuzatamiz.

1920-yilda Bokuda nashr etilgan "Fuqaro fuyuzato" jurnalida e'lon qilingan yuqorida tilga olingan Turkistonda matbuot nomli maqolasida Cho'lpon mahalliy matbuot faoliyati, uning xalq hayoti va siyosiy voqelikda tutgan o'rniga shunday baho bergan edi: Eski vaqtlarda: Matbuot

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yettinchi davlatdir, derlar edi. Bu soʻz, bu da'vo endi-da ahamiyatini yitirmabdir. Bu kunda matbuotning ahamiyati buyukdir. Xususan, Sharq xalqi bu kun matbuotning ahamiyatini tushunmishdir. Buyuk inqilob olamining ketishidan bexabar yotgan sharqliklarni uyg'otmish, qonsiz tomirlariga qon, "yashamak uchun muboraza edajak" muqaddas qon savk etmishdir. Qamoqda matbuotni ajnabiylarga - xorijliklarga maxsus bir "shay" bilan sharqlilar bukun uni izlar, topar, uning ustida mulohaza yuritarlar. Olamning tugul, hatto shaharning hayotiga-da ko'zining ichi bilan boqqan ko'yli, kandli bu kun ko'yning tashqarisida, yiroqlarda tantanali, muborazali va o'ziga ham taalluqli bo'lgan hayotni bilmoq va o'rganmoq istab ta'qib etadilar".

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish lozimki Tukistonda milliy ozodlik uchun xalqni savodli, ma'rifatli qilish uchun ishlab chiqarilgan gazetalar ma'lum muddat bo'lsada yashab xalqni drdini byon qila oldi. Yurtimizning mustaqilligi tufayli biz endilikda tarixiy merosimizni haqqoniy o'rganishga va baholash imkoniyatiga ega bo'ldik. Mustaqil O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Kengashi 1993-yilda "Taraqqiy" gazetasining birinchi soni chiqqan 27 iyun sanasini o'zbek matbuotchilarining kasb bayrami sifatida nishonlash to'g'risida maxsus qaror qabul qildi. Bu milliy matbuotimizning xalqimiz ravnaqidagi beqiyos xizmatiga berilgan munosib bahodir.

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